

Two-Group Power Reactor Noise Theory for Fast Systems

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ABSTRACT

In a new edited book on the surveillance and diagnostics of next generation nuclear reactors [1], the author and his co-editors made an inventory of the existing methods of neutron noise diagnostics of both low and high power nuclear systems. A survey was made on how the currently used methods can be applied to Generation-IV reactors and SMRs, and how they need to be developed further such that they can be used for the next generation of reactors. Such a development was to extend the two-group theory of power reactor noise, traditionally used for thermal systems, to be suitable for use in fast systems with solid fuel. In this paper the extension is described, and some examples of its application to fast systems are shown. As a further development, the extension of the two-group theory to fast spectrum Molten Salt Reactors is also outlined. An open access software, with which the quantitative calculations in Ref. [1] and in this paper were made, is described in the Appendix, and will be demonstrated in the talk.

Keywords: Reactor diagnostics, power reactor noise, fast reactors, two-group noise theory

1. INTRODUCTION

In the theory of power reactor noise diagnostics simple models of the neutron noise have been very useful. These use a one-dimensional homogeneous bare core with one average group of delayed neutrons, and two energy groups. Earlier, such simple models were necessary to use in order to get analytical solutions, as well as a simple analytical representation of the noise sources, in order to solve the inverse task, i.e. unfolding the noise source parameters from the induced neutron noise. Although with the advancement of machine learning methods the inverse task can be solved even if only numerical solutions of the direct task are available, the significance of the simple models has not diminished. The reason is that a two-group approach captures the significant aspects of the system response with high fidelity, and the transparent solutions provided by simple models are essential in judging the possibilities of the diagnostics, i.e. the unfolding of the parameters of the perturbation from the measured neutron noise. One particular aspect to be investigated is whether the system response, expressed by its transfer or Green's function, is dominated by a point kinetic or a space-dependent response, because the latter case is the pre-requisite that localised perturbations could be diagnosed.

Two-group power reactor noise theory so far was only used for thermal light water reactors, and to some extent for heavy water reactors. For such systems, use of two-group theory to describe the behavior of the fast and thermal neutrons is completely straightforward and justified. However, most of the Gen-IV reactors, and many of the planned SMRs, will be fast reactors with a hard spectrum. In these cores the thermal flux will be vanishingly small, and traditional two-group theory cannot be applied. To realise the same advantages of transparency and interpretability described above, there is still a need for a two-group noise theory for fast systems. The subject of this paper is to present and demonstrate the development of a simple analytical theory of power reactor noise using two energy groups, and to demonstrate its use. The two-group noise theory for fast reactors with solid fuel was recently developed in a newly published book by the author and colleagues [1]. The theory and some results will be reproduced here, and the extension for fast fluid fuel reactors (MSRs) is outlined.

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2. TWO-GROUP POWER REACTOR NOISE THEORY

2.1. Two-group noise theory for thermal systems

The equations for the space-frequency dependent neutron noise, $\delta\phi(x, \omega)$, which are obtained from the time-dependent equations for the flux and the precursors, after subtracting the static equations, neglecting second order terms and eliminating the precursors after a Fourier transform, read as [2]

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_1 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_1(\omega) & v \Sigma_{f2}(\omega) \\ \Sigma_R & D_2 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_2(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta\phi_1(x, \omega) \\ \delta\phi_2(x, \omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1(x, \omega) \\ S_2(x, \omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Here, the following standard notations and definitions were used:

$$\Sigma_{f,i}(\omega) = \Sigma_{f,i} \left(1 - \frac{i\omega\beta}{\lambda + i\omega} \right) \equiv \beta(\omega) \Sigma_{f,i}; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (2)$$

$$\Sigma_1(\omega) = \Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_R + \frac{i\omega}{v_1} - v \Sigma_{f1}(\omega) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\Sigma_2(\omega) = \Sigma_{a2} + \frac{i\omega}{v_2} \quad (4)$$

The noise sources $S_1(x, \omega)$ and $S_2(x, \omega)$ are defined in terms of the cross section fluctuations and the static fluxes as follows:

$$S_1(x, \omega) = \left[\delta\Sigma_R(x, \omega) + \delta\Sigma_{a1}(x, \omega) - \delta v \Sigma_{f1}(x, \omega) \beta(\omega) \right] \phi_1(x) - \delta v \Sigma_{f2}(x, \omega) \beta(\omega) \phi_2(x) \quad (5)$$

and

$$S_2(x, \omega) = -\delta\Sigma_R(x, \omega) \phi_1(x) + \delta\Sigma_{a2}(x, \omega) \phi_2(x). \quad (6)$$

Eq. (1) can be written in a compact operator form as

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}(x, \omega) \vec{\delta\phi}(x, \omega) = \vec{S}(x, \omega) \quad (7)$$

The equation for the Green's matrix $\hat{\mathbf{G}}(x, x', \omega)$ of Eq. (1), in terms of Eq. (7) can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}(x, \omega) \hat{\mathbf{G}}(x, x', \omega) = \hat{\mathbf{I}} \delta(x - x'), \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ is the 2×2 unit matrix. From Eqs (7) and (8) the noise can be obtained in a symbolic form as:

$$\vec{\delta\phi}(x, \omega) = \int \hat{\mathbf{G}}(x, x', \omega) \vec{S}(x', \omega) dx'. \quad (9)$$

The above formulae, together with the way how the static group constants are generated, reflect the specific properties of thermal systems. The energy separation between the two groups is at the upper level of the energy of thermalised neutrons, usually 0.625 eV, and the group constants are generated with this energy separation when collapsing them from a multigroup set. Further, both the prompt and delayed neutrons are born into the fast group. These are the two points on which the theory need to be changed in order to become suitable for applications in fast systems, i.e. both the input data and the formulae need to be modified. This will be described below.

2.2. Fast systems (solid fuel reactors)

As mentioned above and as it is obvious, a two-group theory with a group below and one above the thermal energy 0.625 eV is meaningless in a fast systems. A practical suggestion for the static two-group theory of fast system was given by Meem [3], who suggests to choose the energy separation between the two groups at the threshold of fast fission. The threshold for ^{238}U is around 1 MeV, but the threshold is not sharp, and Meem suggests to use 1.35 MeV, which we also adopted in our quantitative work. This choice appears plausible and also practical from the measurement point of view (using fast fission chambers for detecting the noise in the fast group). The optimum energy threshold could be actually found by varying it and comparing the results with multigroup or Monte-Carlo calculations. Such a study is outside of the scope of this work, but will definitely be done in the future.

For the quantitative work, homogenized and collapsed 2-group cross sections were generated with the Serpent2 continuous energy Monte Carlo code [4]. In the simulations, the JEFF 3.1 cross section library was used, whereas the thermal scattering data were adopted from JEFF 3.3. The intermediate multi-group structure was set to the Scale-252 structure, and the final 2-group constants were collapsed without critical spectrum correction. The leakage spectrum correction was performed outside of the Serpent calculation. The energy boundary between group 2 and 1, i.e. the slow/epithermal and fast energy groups, was set to 1.35 MeV for fast systems. Uppscattering was neglected throughout.

Obviously, with an energy separation of 1.35 MeV, group 2 does not correspond to the thermal neutrons, rather to the epithermal ones. The idea of using two groups here is that this model can still capture the local component in a fast system, if there is any.

The second modification concerns the fact that with the energy separation of 1.35 MeV, both the prompt and the delayed neutrons will appear both in group 1 and 2 with the corresponding spectral weights. Correspondingly, we define

$\chi_{p,i}$ - fraction of prompt neutrons appearing in group $i = \{1,2\}$;

$\chi_{d,i}$ - fraction of delayed neutrons appearing in group $i = \{1,2\}$.

The equation for the neutron noise in the two groups will read as

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_1 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_1(\omega) & v \Sigma_{f2}(\omega) \\ \Sigma_{R2}(\omega) & D_2 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_2(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \phi_1(x, \omega) \\ \delta \phi_2(x, \omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1(x, \omega) \\ S_2(x, \omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Here, the following notations were used:

$$\chi_{1,2}(\omega) = \chi_{p1,2}(1 - \beta) + \chi_{d1,2} \frac{\lambda \beta}{i \omega + \lambda}, \quad (11)$$

$$\Sigma_1(\omega) = \Sigma_{a1} + \frac{i \omega}{v_1} + \Sigma_R - \chi_1(\omega) v \Sigma_{f1}, \quad \Sigma_2(\omega) = \Sigma_{a2} + \frac{i \omega}{v_2} - \chi_2(\omega) v \Sigma_{f2}, \quad (12)$$

$$\Sigma_{R2}(\omega) = \Sigma_R + \chi_2(\omega) v \Sigma_{f1} \quad \text{and} \quad \Sigma_{f2}(\omega) = \chi_1(\omega) v \Sigma_{f2}. \quad (13)$$

The components of the noise source are given as

$$S_1(x, \omega) = \left(\delta \Sigma_{a1}(x, \omega) + \delta \Sigma_R(x, \omega) - \chi_1(\omega) \delta v \Sigma_{f1}(x, \omega) \right) \phi_1(x) - \chi_1(\omega) \delta v \Sigma_{f2}(x, \omega) \phi_2(x) \quad (14)$$

and

$$S_2(x, \omega) = - \left(\delta \Sigma_R(x, \omega) + \chi_2(\omega) \delta v \Sigma_{f1}(\omega) \right) \phi_1(x) + \left(\delta \Sigma_{a2}(x, \omega) - \chi_2(\omega) \delta v \Sigma_{f2} \right) \phi_2(x). \quad (15)$$

The equation for the Green's matrix has the same symbolic form as in (8), except that $\hat{\mathbf{L}}(x, \omega)$ is now defined by the matrix operator in (10). The equation can be solved columnwise for the Green's matrix,

and the solution reads as follows. Denoting the two roots of the characteristic equation of (10) as $\mu^2(\omega)$ and $-\nu^2(\omega)$, define the basic solutions

$$g_\mu(x, x', \omega) = \begin{cases} \sin[\mu(\omega)(a+x)] \sin[\mu(\omega)(a-x)]; & x < x'; \\ \sin[\mu(\omega)(a-x)] \sin[\mu(\omega)(a+x)]; & x > x'; \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

and

$$g_\nu(x, x', \omega) = \begin{cases} \sinh[\nu(\omega)(a+x)] \sinh[\nu(\omega)(a-x)]; & x < x'; \\ \sinh[\nu(\omega)(a-x)] \sinh[\nu(\omega)(a+x)]; & x > x'; \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Then, one has

$$\begin{bmatrix} G_{11}(x, x', \omega) \\ G_{12}(x, x', \omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\mu(\omega) \end{bmatrix} A_{\mu 1}(\omega) g_\mu(x, x', \omega) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\nu(\omega) \end{bmatrix} A_{\nu 1}(\omega) g_\nu(x, x', \omega) \quad (18)$$

with

$$A_{\mu 1}(\omega) = \frac{c_\mu(\omega) \nu \Sigma_{f2}(\omega)}{D_1^2 \mu(\omega) \sin[2\mu(\omega)a] (\mu^2(\omega) + \nu^2(\omega))'} \quad (19)$$

$$A_{\nu 1}(\omega) = \frac{c_\mu(\omega) \nu \Sigma_{f2}(\omega)}{D_1^2 \nu(\omega) \sinh[2\nu(\omega)a] (\mu^2(\omega) + \nu^2(\omega))'} \quad (20)$$

$$c_\mu(\omega) = \frac{\Sigma_1(\omega) + D_1 \mu^2(\omega)}{\nu \Sigma_{f2}(\omega)} \quad \text{and} \quad c_\nu(\omega) = \frac{\Sigma_1(\omega) - D_1 \nu^2(\omega)}{\nu \Sigma_{f2}(\omega)} \quad (21)$$

A similar form of the solution is obtained for the second column of the Green's function matrix, except that $A_{\mu 1}(\omega)$ and $A_{\nu 1}(\omega)$ will be replaced with the coefficients $A_{\mu 2}(\omega)$ and $A_{\nu 2}(\omega)$.

Actually, the above represents the general solution for both fast and thermal systems, because substituting $\chi_{p1} = \chi_{d1} = 1$ and $\chi_{p2} = \chi_{d2} = 0$, they become identical with those for the thermal system. This is valid for both the Green's function, as well as for the noise source. For fast systems, both $\chi_{p1}, \chi_{d1}, \chi_{p2}$ and χ_{d2} will be neither zero nor unity, rather they need to be calculated according to the energy threshold selected.

3. RESULTS

For illustrations, we will show two selected cases, namely a thermal system (a commercial BWR, simulated in the axial direction) and a medium size fluoride fast core. This latter is a conceptual core for demonstration purposes, inspired by the SAMOFAR design, having a fluoride salt fuel with $\text{LiF}_4 - \text{UF}_4$ mixture. The fuel velocity was chosen as zero, such that the methods of solid fuel cores could be applied.

Two kinds of plots will be shown: the space dependence of the absolute value and the phase of the four elements of the Green's matrices at a fixed frequency at the plateau region, and the frequency dependence of the same for $x = x' = 0$. The plots for the space dependence for both systems are shown in Fig. 1 and for the frequency dependence in Fig. 2. For easy comparison, the left hand side plots in both figures show the thermal system, and the right hand side plots the fast system.

The left columns of Figs. 1 and 2 show a behaviour characteristic of a large thermal system. The deviation of the space dependence of the absolute values from the cosine shaped static flux (not shown here for brevity) indicates a significant deviation from point kinetic behaviour. A small local component is seen in G_{22} , which connects the perturbation in the thermal group with the noise in the thermal group. The amplitudes of the fast components G_{11} and G_{12} , are larger than those of the thermal components G_{21} and G_{22} , similarly to the fact that the fast static flux is larger than the thermal one. The frequency

Figure 1. Space dependence of the amplitude and the phase of the components of the Green's function for $x_0 = 0$ and $\omega = 10$ rad/s for a commercial BWR (left column) and for a medium sized fluoride salt fast core

Figure 2. Frequency dependence of the amplitude and the phase of the components of the Green's function for $x_0 = x = 0$ for a commercial BWR (left column) and for a medium fluoride salt fast core

dependence of the amplitude and the phase shows the typical plateau behaviour between $\omega = \lambda$ and $\omega = \beta/\Lambda$, i.e. between 0.1 and 100 rad/s.

The right columns of Figs 1 and 2 show the space and frequency dependence of the amplitude and the phase of the four components of the Green's function for a fast system. Although the size of this system is larger than that of the BWR, the spatial dependence of the amplitude indicates that the deviation from point kinetic behaviour is milder than in the thermal system. Further, the figures show that the relationships between the group 1 and group 2 components are reversed to those for the thermal system. Namely, the amplitudes of the components in group 2, G_{21} and G_{22} , are larger than those in group 1, G_{11} and G_{12} . Even if the meaning of group 1 and 2 is not identical for the fast and the thermal systems, this shift is interesting. In addition, the local component is now seen in G_{11} . From the frequency dependence (Fig. 2) it is seen that the plateau region is much wider in the fast system than in the thermal one, as expected. These results indicate that small size fast reactors, such as fast spectrum SMRs, are going to exhibit a strong point kinetic behaviour, which will severely limit the efficiency of locating localised perturbations.

4. TWO-GROUP THEORY OF FAST MSRS

The equations for an MSR are more involved than for solid fuel reactors. The speed of the fuel flow in the core of height H and external loop length L is denoted by u , and the transit time in the core and the external loop are denoted as $\tau_c = H/u$ and $\tau_L = L/u$, respectively, with the total recirculation time being $\tau = \tau_c + \tau_L = T/u$, where $T = H + L$ is the total length of the loop. With the above spectral definitions of the prompt and delayed spectral indices $\chi_{p,i}$ and $\chi_{d,i}$, the static two-group equations for an MSR read as follows in the x coordinate system, with the system boundaries at $x = \pm a$:

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 \nabla^2 \phi_1(x) - (\Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_R) \phi_1(x) + \chi_{p1} \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} (1 - \beta) \phi_1(x) + \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta) \phi_2(x) \right] + \chi_{d1} \lambda C_0(x) &= 0 \\ D_2 \nabla^2 \phi_2(x) - \Sigma_{a2} \phi_2(x) + \Sigma_R \phi_1(x) + \chi_{p2} \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} (1 - \beta) \phi_1(x) + \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta) \phi_2(x) \right] + \chi_{d2} \lambda C_0(x) &= 0 \\ u \frac{dC_0(x)}{dx} = \beta \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x) + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x) \right] - \lambda C_0(x) & \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The boundary conditions are the vanishing of the fluxes at the extrapolated boundaries, whereas for the precursors one has

$$C_0(-x) = C_0(x) e^{-\lambda \tau_L} \quad (23)$$

The third equation above, concerning the delayed neutron precursors, is the same as for the case of thermal MSRs, except that now fast fission is also accounted for. If it was neglected, the equation would be exactly the same. The solution for $C_0(x)$ in terms of the fluxes is also the same, except that $\nu \Sigma_f \phi_2(x)$ is replaced by $\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x) + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x)$:

$$\begin{aligned} C_0(x) = e^{-\frac{x\lambda}{u}} \frac{\beta}{u} \left(\frac{1}{e^{\lambda\tau} - 1} \int_{-a}^a e^{\frac{x'\lambda}{u}} \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x') + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x') \right] dx' + \right. \\ \left. \int_{-a}^x e^{\frac{\lambda x'}{u}} \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x') + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x') \right] dx' \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Analytical solution can only be obtained in the prompt recirculation (infinite fuel velocity) approximation [1], in which case the above will simplify to

$$C_0(x) = \frac{\beta}{\lambda T} \int_{-a}^a \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x') + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x') \right] dx'. \quad (25)$$

Substituting (25) into the first two equations of (24), as well as introducing the notations

$$\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_R - \chi_{p1} \nu \Sigma_{f1} (1 - \beta), \quad (26)$$

$$\Sigma_2 = \Sigma_{a2} - \chi_{p2} \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta), \quad (27)$$

$$\Sigma_{R2} = \Sigma_R + \chi_{p2} \nu \Sigma_{f1} (1 - \beta), \quad (28)$$

one obtains the static equations for the fast and slow flux in a matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_1 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_1 & \chi_{p1} \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta) \\ \Sigma_{R2} & D_2 \nabla^2 - \Sigma_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(x) \\ \phi_2(x) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \chi_{d1} \\ \chi_{d2} \end{bmatrix} \frac{\beta}{T} \int_{-a}^a \left[\nu \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1(x') + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2(x') \right] dx'. \quad (29)$$

The matrix on the left hand side of (29) is formally the same as for a traditional reactor, except that $\chi_1 \nu \Sigma_{f2}$ is replaced by $\chi_{p1} \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta)$, and of course that the definitions of the parameters Σ_1 and Σ_2 are different. But the formal similarity helps to easily write down the coupling coefficients c_μ and c_ν (see below). Further, similarly to the case of the thermal MSR with only thermal fission, the right hand side is still constant, even if, due to accounting for fast fission, both fluxes appear in the integral, and that the inhomogeneous part appears in the equations of both the fast and the slow flux.

These latter differences notwithstanding, the path for the solution for the fluxes and for the criticality equation is the same as for the thermal MSR, even if the final results will be different. The general solution of the homogeneous equation is the same as for the thermal system, described in [1], and the particular solution of the inhomogeneous equation is still a constant. Hence, the general solution has exactly the same form as for the thermal MSRs:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(x) \\ \phi_2(x) \end{bmatrix} = A \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\mu \end{bmatrix} (\cos(\mu x) - \cos(\mu a)) + B \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ c_\nu \end{bmatrix} (\cosh(\nu x) - \cosh(\nu a)) \quad (30)$$

where the coupling coefficients c_μ and c_ν differ from their thermal MSR counterparts:

$$c_\mu = \frac{\Sigma_{R2}}{\Sigma_2 + D_2 \mu^2} = \frac{\Sigma_1 + D_1 \mu^2}{\chi_{p1} \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta)} \quad (31)$$

and

$$c_\nu = \frac{\Sigma_{R2}}{\Sigma_2 - D_2 \nu^2} = \frac{\Sigma_1 - D_1 \nu^2}{\chi_{p1} \nu \Sigma_{f2} (1 - \beta)} \quad (32)$$

The difference in the solutions will be in the ratio between A and B , as well as in the form of the criticality equation. The procedure is that using (30) in one of the equations of (29) will yield a relationship between the coefficients A and B , then eliminating one of the coefficients with this and using the resulting expression in the other equation of (29) will yield the criticality equation. These will both be much more complicated than for the case of the thermal MSR with only thermal fission.

The space and frequency-dependent equations for the neutron noise can be described in a similar way, and can be solved with the same methodology as for the thermal MSR. The results will be reported at the conference.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The above shows that the generalised analytical theory of power reactor noise in two groups can reveal interesting differences between the noise in fast and thermal systems. With the formalism developed, the Green's function components were calculated for a number of Gen-IV systems and SMRs, and their dynamical response was analysed. In addition, the neutron noise in groups 1 and 2, induced by various characteristic perturbations (variable strength absorber, vibrating fuel pin/absorber rod, and propagating perturbations) were calculated and the possibility of their quantification from the measured neutron noise was investigated. Here only a minor fraction of the results could be shown, more results will be presented in the talk. The open access Wolfram Mathematica code, used for the numerical work in this paper and in Ref. [1] (see Appendix A below) will also be demonstrated.

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APPENDIX A.

All calculations and plots in Chapters 3 and 4 in Ref. [1], from which the above Figures were also reproduced, were made by a Wolfram Mathematica Notebook. A streamlined and user friendly version of the notebook is uploaded to the Wolfram Notebook Archive, from where it is freely accessible and downloadable through the link

<https://notebookarchive.org/2025-05-7dypmeq>

The input data needed to run the code for each system studied are collected from a public GitHub repository and can be selected by the user. These files are also available from the open access source Mendeley Data [5] and from a public GitHub repository.

Interested readers who do not have access to Mathematica, can run the downloaded Notebook with the open access software Wolfram Player, available for free from

<https://www.wolfram.com/player/>

Alternatively, the Notebook can be run directly on-line in the Wolfram Cloud. To do this one needs to have an account, for which one can sign up for free at

<https://www.wolframcloud.com/>

The code in the Notebook can be changed by the user, which makes it possible to make calculations with changed input parameters, i.e, study the same systems as in above, but with some parameters changed, or make calculations for new systems, or just change the format of the plots of the existing calculations. One particular option is to change the size of the core, to check how the dynamic properties of the system transfer change if a specific full-size Gen-IV core was converted into an SMR or vice versa.